

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Full paper

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

All papers published in this conference proceedings have been peer reviewed through a peer review process administered by the proceedings Editors. Reviews were conducted by expert referees to the professional and scientific standards expected of a conference proceedings.

Proceeding Editors

Nicolas Robinson-Garcia
Daniel Torres-Salinas
Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado

Citation: Stephen, D. (2022). Comparison of the citations of German medical science articles in questionable and non-questionable journals. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti22144).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6975638>

Copyright: © 2022 the authors, © 2022 Faculty of Communication and Documentation, University of Granada, Spain. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#).

Collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sti2022grx/>

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Comparison of the citations of German medical science articles in questionable and non-questionable journals

Dimity Stephen*

*stephen@dzhw.eu

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies, Schützenstr 6a, Berlin, 10117 (Germany)

Introduction

Questionable journals (QJs), also known as predatory journals, are journals that demonstrate “dishonest tendencies, lack scientific rigor, and function primarily for financial gain” (Kurt, 2018). Although the push toward open-access publishing is fundamentally a positive movement toward transparency and inclusivity in academia, it has allowed QJs to flourish in recent years (Richtig et al., 2018). Under the guise of open-access, amongst other questionable practices such as spamming researchers for submissions and falsely claiming metrics and/or indexation in respectable databases, QJs typically charge article processing fees while performing no or only cursory peer review (Björk, Kanto-Karvonen & Harviainen, 2020). Publishing in QJs can be problematic as this content is typically not indexed in reputable databases, thereby reducing articles’ visibility and potential impact and squandering funding spent on publishing fees. However, the most concerning aspect of QJs is arguably the lack of adequate peer review. Many consumers of academic journals are either unaware of the concept of questionable journals or cannot identify them. For instance, a third of surveyed oncologists in Germany and Austria were unaware of predatory journals, and around half who said they were aware of QJs still could not identify one (Richtig et al., 2018). This is particularly concerning as over 90% of practitioners reported using journal articles to inform their day-to-day treatment decisions (Richtig et al., 2018). Consequently, as researchers may not recognise questionable journals, articles that have not undergone adequate peer review can be cited by articles in non-questionable journals and become legitimised, proliferating dubious, or even potentially harmful (Oermann et al., 2017), research.

This study aimed to investigate the profile and citation impact of research in questionable journals authored by researchers at German institutions. Researchers from low- and middle-income countries often constitute the majority of authors in QJs (e.g. Kurt, 2018; Cobey et al., 2019). However, more than 5,000 researchers in Germany recently published in QJs (Offord, 2018) and up to 40% of authors in QJs are from high-income countries (Cohen et al., 2019), indicating that the publication practices of authors from high-income countries may also warrant examination. Previous studies investigating the citation impact of articles in QJs have found that such articles typically remained uncited more often (Björk et al., 2020) and received substantially fewer citations than similar articles in non-QJs (Björk et al., 2020; Moussa, 2020, Akca & Akbulut, 2021). However, it appears that no study has yet examined the citation impact of research in questionable journals from specifically high-income countries, such as Germany. This study compared the citation impact and countries of co-

authors and authors citing German-authored medical and health science articles in QJs against a comparable sample of German-authored articles in non-QJs to examine the patterns and differences in citation impact between these groups.

Methods

QJs were defined as those included in Cabell's Predatory Reports (CPR). Launched in 2017, CPR is a subscription-based database of over 16,000 journals classified via manual review as "predatory" based on more than 60 indicators of publishing practices, such as peer review and metrics usage (Cabells, n.d.). To identify German research in QJs, all journals in which authors from German institutions published between 2010 and 2020 were identified in Dimensions. Dimensions was used as the basis for bibliometric data because it contains a broader sample of research than the restricted, quality-controlled content in Scopus and Web of Science (WoS; Visser, van Eck, & Waltman, 2021). To reduce the sample of journals to be checked against CPR, journals from Dimensions were matched to those in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and in WoS, as entities in these sources can reliably be considered non-questionable. Data from Dimensions were supplied by Digital Science as a snapshot of data up to April 2021. DOAJ data were obtained from the public data dump for January 25, 2022. Data from WoS were obtained from the German Competence Network for Bibliometrics' in-house version of the database, which covers data until April 2021. Journal titles were fuzzy matched between the sources using the *fuzzyjoin* package (Robinson, 2020) in R (R Core Team, 2020) and a threshold Levenshtein distance of 6. Matches with distances between 3 and 6 were manually confirmed, and all matches were removed from the sample. Journals from known reputable publishers, such as Springer, Wiley, and De Gruyter, were also excluded. The remaining journal titles were manually searched in CPR and for all matches, the number and type of violations provided for classifying the journals as questionable were recorded from CPR.

Metadata of all articles with German authors published 2010-2020 in journals matched with CPR were then extracted from Dimensions, including all authors' names, the article's discipline, and 3-year and total citation counts. Metadata of all documents citing these articles in QJs were also extracted from Dimensions, including authors' names, country-level affiliations, and publishing journal. The journals citing articles in QJs were also searched in CPR to identify if they too were questionable. To identify instances of self-citation, authors' and citing authors' names were cleaned of punctuation and first and surnames merged, and these names were then fuzzy matched using a threshold Levenshtein distance of 8. All matches were manually checked for accuracy. Self-citations were calculated on the basis of any author of the article in the QJ citing themselves, not just the author affiliated with the German institution.

As a control group against which to compare the characteristics of articles in QJs, I randomly sampled from Dimensions 348 German-authored articles published in 2010-2018 in non-questionable OA journals that were classified as Medical and Health Sciences (MHS) articles. Articles were restricted to MHS to ensure the effect of disciplinary citation practices was controlled for and MHS was the only discipline with an adequate number of articles for analysis in the QJ sample (348 articles published until 2018, allowing a 3-year citation window). OA journals were selected to ensure equivalence of a potential citation advantage of OA journals, as all QJs were OA. Eligible journals were identified by matching the journals with German-authored articles from Dimensions with the DOAJ list, as verified legitimate OA journals. Nature and PLoS journals were excluded as these highly cited, high-output journals are not representative of OA journals and could skew the control group. A random

sample of 348 articles was then drawn from these journals. The same process of extracting metadata from Dimensions and identifying self-citations was undertaken for this control group. As expected, the distributions of citations in both samples were skewed toward 0 and therefore not normally distributed. As such, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon test was used to compare the 3-year citations between the QJ and non-QJ groups.

Results

In total, 88 questionable journals with German-authored articles indexed in Dimensions were identified. The mean number of violations CPR attributed to the questionable journals was 4.8 (range = 1-8, IQR = 3.8-6.0). The most common violations were in relation to publication practises (70, 79.5%), peer review (59, 67.0%), websites (57, 64.8%), and access and copyright conditions (43, 48.9%). Between 2010 and 2020, 591 articles were published in these journals by authors affiliated with German institutions. The peak numbers were published in 2014 and 2015 when 85 and 87 articles appeared. The number of articles declined sharply after 2017 to 19 in 2020, the lowest level over the time-series. This decline coincided with the peak incidence of informational articles about predatory publishing (Krawczyk & Kulczycki, 2021), and may reflect changes in publishing practices due to increased awareness of questionable journals. Articles in QJs represented less than 0.1% of all research produced by Germany annually. Allowing for multiple assignments, three-quarters (449, 76.0%) of the articles were in the MHS field, followed by 13.4% (79) in natural sciences, 5.4% (32) in engineering and technology, 3.9% (23) in social sciences, 1.8% (11) in agricultural sciences, and 0.7% (4) were in the humanities.

Analyses of citation counts and country profiles of co-authors and citing authors were based the 348 articles classified to the MHS field and published between 2010 and 2018 and the corresponding sample of 348 German-authored MHS articles in non-questionable OA journals. The articles in QJs received 3,481 citations from 3,407 distinct articles in 1,736 journals, while the articles in non-QJs received 8,846 citations from 8,825 distinct articles in 2,869 journals. Self-citations accounted for 12.3% (428) of the citations received by the articles in QJs, which was slightly lower than the rate of 15.6% (1,376) self-citations observed for articles in non-QJs. Only 5.1% of citations to articles in QJs were from articles in journals also considered questionable. Forty-two articles in QJs (12.1%) were uncited three years after publication, compared to 8.3% (29) of MHS articles in non-QJs. The mean 3-year citations of articles in QJs and non-QJs were 4.6 and 10.2, respectively, while mean total citations – i.e. not just those received in the first three years – were 10.0 and 25.4, respectively. The distributions of the 3-year citations of the articles in both groups are shown in Figure 1. Articles in questionable journals received significantly fewer citations within 3 years of publication than articles in non-questionable OA journals ($p < 0.001$).

The left panel of Figure 2 shows the percentage of German-authored MHS articles in QJs and non-QJs that were co-authored with countries that co-published more than 1% of articles in at least one of the journal groups. Some countries, such as Israel, did not co-publish any articles in QJs and so therefore do not have data points for this group. Whole counting of co-authors was applied at the level of countries, therefore the percentages do not sum to 100%.

Notably, the countries with which German authors collaborated were similar between groups, although the extent of collaboration was typically reduced for articles published in questionable journals. For example, 17.5% of articles in non-questionable journals were co-authored with the United States, however an American co-author was only present on 7.8% of articles in questionable journals. Similarly large decreases were evident for other key

collaboration partners such as Switzerland, the United Kingdom, and the Netherlands. These reductions align with the tendency for articles in QJs to be national outputs: only 24.7% (86) of these articles involved international collaboration compared to 57.5% (200) of articles in non-QJs. Exceptions to this trend are Belgium, Greece, and India, with which German authors co-published slightly more articles in QJs than non-QJs.

Figure 1. Distributions of 3-year citations of MHS articles published in QJs and non-QJs between 2010 and 2018. Note: excludes 5 articles in non-QJs with 64-247 citations.

The right panel of Figure 2 shows selected countries' fractional share of articles citing articles in QJs and non-QJs. These countries are those that accounted for more than 1% of citing articles in one or both of the journal groups. Fractional counting was applied at the level of the author and aggregated to country level. This panel excludes 5% and 7% of articles citing non-QJs and QJs, respectively, that did not have any information about the authors' affiliations. As with co-authorship, the patterns of countries citing articles was similar between groups. Only the United States, the United Kingdom, and Switzerland showed notable reductions in their share of citations of articles in questionable versus non-questionable journals. Conversely, China, Italy, Japan, and South Korea accounted for higher shares of citations to articles in questionable journals than they did non-questionable journals. Germany itself accounted for 15.2%-15.4% of citations in each group.

Discussion

This study identified 591 articles published in 88 questionable journals between 2010 and 2020 by researchers from German institutions. Three-quarters of German research in QJs was in the medical and health sciences. However, this may reflect that a substantial proportion of research from both Germany and indexed in Dimensions is medical research, rather than a greater propensity for research in this field to appear in QJs. Regardless, the presence of medical research in QJs raises concerns given that most medical practitioners in Germany and Austria rely on current publications to inform their treatment decisions, and half acknowledge that they are unaware of and/or cannot recognise QJs (Richtig et al., 2018). Further, the majority of the research in QJs had been cited at least once within 3 years of publication by a diverse array of predominantly reputable journals, with only 12% remaining uncited. This was

only slightly less than the rate for articles in non-QJs (8%), and substantially lower than other samples of research in questionable journals that found 25% to 56% were uncited (Bagues, Sylos-Labini & Zinovyena, 2019; Björk et al., 2020). Authors' self-citations accounted for only a portion (12%) of this uptake, and less than in the non-QJ sample (16%). Overall, articles in QJs were significantly less impactful than articles in non-QJs, however there was still a reasonably high level of uptake of research in QJs.

Figure 2. Countries' percent of articles co-authored (left), and countries' fractional shares of citations (right) to German-authored MHS articles in QJs and non-QJs.

In terms of co-authorship, the countries German authors co-published with were similar between articles in QJs and non-QJs, although there was substantially less international collaboration involved in QJ articles. The countries citing German research were also similar

for both sets of articles, indicating articles in QJs are being used in a wide range of subsequent international research, although to a lesser extent than similar articles from non-QJs.

The substantial uptake of research in QJs by authors in a diverse set of countries and journals may reflect authors' lack of awareness of QJs, or alternatively, may suggest that the quality of the research is acceptable, despite its publishing venue. Although these articles appear in journals that have displayed questionable practices and may be insufficiently reviewed, this does not necessarily reflect the quality of the article and underlying research itself. Authors may publish in QJs for a variety of reasons, such as shorter times to publication, not simply to avoid peer review of subpar research. Also, citation counts are not informative about the reason for citing the study, which may also occur as authors disagree with or critique the study in the QJ, rather than support it. Additional research is required to examine the quality of research in QJs, to understand the motivations of authors to publish in QJs, and the reasons for citing these articles. Such studies would further our understanding of the impact on the academic community of the use of QJs and the proliferation of their content.

References

Akca, S., & Akbulut, M. (2021). Are predatory journals contaminating science? An analysis on the Cabells' Predatory Report. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 47(4), 102366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2021.102366>

Bagues, M., Sylos-Labini, M., & Zinovyena, N. (2019). A walk on the wild side: 'Predatory' journals and information asymmetries in scientific evaluations. *Research Policy*, 48(2), 462-477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.04.013>

Björk, B-C., Kanto-Karvonen, S., & Harviainen, J. T (2020). How frequently are articles in predatory Open Access journals cited. *Publications*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications8020017>

Cabells. (n.d.). Predatory Reports. Cabells. Retrieved February 28, 2022, from <https://www2.cabells.com/about-predatory>

Cobey, K., Grudniewicz, A., Lalu, M., Rice, D., Raffoul, H., & Moher, D. (2019). Knowledge and motivations of researchers publishing in presumed predatory journals: a survey. *BMJ Open*, 9(3), e026516. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-026516>

Krawczyk, F., & Kulczycki, E. (2021). How is open access accused of being predatory? The impact of Beall's lists of predatory journals on academic publishing. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 47(2), 102271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2020.102271>

Kurt, S. (2018). Why do authors publish in predatory journals? *Learned Publishing*, 31(2), 141-147. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1150>

Moussa, S. (2021). Citation contagion: a citation analysis of selected predatory marketing journals. *Scientometrics*, 126(1), 485-506. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03729-6>

Oermann, M., Nicoll, L., Chinn, P., Ashton, K., Conklin, J., Edie, A., Amarasekara III, S., & Williams, B. (2017). Quality of articles published in predatory nursing journals. *Nursing Outlook*, 66(4), 4-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.outlook.2017.05.005>

R Core Team. (2020). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>

Robinson, D. (2020). fuzzyjoin: Join Tables Together on Inexact Matching. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=fuzzyjoin>

Visser, M., van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2021). Large-scale comparison of bibliographic data sources: Scopus, Web of Science, Dimensions, Crossref, and Microsoft Academic. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 2(1), 20-41. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00112